

A REVIEW OF LITERATURE ON PREVENTIVE EFFORTS TO PREVENT SEXUAL VIOLENCE IN ADOLESCENTS: SEXUALITY EDUCATION INTEGRATED IN SOCIOLOGY LEARNING

Erianjoni ^{1*}, Anton Komaini ², Alfajri Yusra ³, Eka Asih Febriani ⁴,
Muhammad Hidayat ⁵, Deski Beri ⁶ and Chici Cania Afdani ⁷

^{1,2,3,4,5,6,7} Universitas Negeri Padang, Padang, Indonesia.

*Corresponding Author Email: erianjonisosologi@gmail.com

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Abstract

This article aims to determine the Forms of Sexual Violence (FoSV) that occur in the school environment and how to model the integration of sex education into the curriculum and subjects. The method used is Literature Review, the literature review sources are taken from several reputable international journal databases and National Science and Technology Index (SINTA) accredited journals. Data was obtained through reviewing several articles from a total of 45 literature reviews. The research results show that: 1) Various forms of violence can occur in different contexts; 2) Integrate sex education into the curriculum and extracurricular activities; 3) integrate comprehensive sexuality education and training to integrate sex education in subjects for teachers, 4) Recommend a model of integration of sexual education in sociology subjects in high school that connects relevant facts, concepts, principles and procedures, which aims to help students understand and deal with sexual violence in a social context. Several models of integrating sexual education are applied to subjects and implementing sexual education programs at every level of education, which aims to provide knowledge and understanding about the impact of sexual violence on individuals, especially women and children, which helps deal with sexual violence that occurs in the school environment and community environment.

Keywords: Sexuality Education, Sociology Learning, Sexual Violence, Integrated.

INTRODUCTION

Nowadays, the issue of whether or not sexuality education materials should be included in the school curriculum is a discourse that often appears in the mass media and in seminars and discussion forums. This discourse is based on several studies conducted showing that sexual violence against teenagers tends to occur and is at an alarming level [1].

This is due to the lack of knowledge of teachers, parents and adolescents related to education, as well as a culture that considers taboo regarding sexuality education is one of the triggers why sexual violence can occur in adolescents [2].

This has resulted in different views on the definition of sexual violence among adolescents. In student groups (adolescents), they generally confuse sexual violence with violence in general. Sexual violence for them is the same as the many violent shows that often appear on television, such as murder, robbery and so on [3]. Meanwhile, groups of adolescent anthropologists, adolescent doctors, adolescent legal experts, and non-governmental organizations (NGOs) have differentiated sexual violence with several stages.

According to them, sexual violence starts from harassing words to genital penetration. However, all research subjects agreed that sexual violence against teenagers is dangerous, traumatic, has physical, psychological and social impacts.

A similar thing happened in the city of Beijing, China. Based on the results of research conducted by Zhang et al, (2015) shows that preschool teachers in China have limited knowledge about preventing Child Sexual Abuse (CSA) [4]. Of 245 preschool teachers, less than 5% had attended a CSA prevention training program. By developing appropriate prevention training programs for preschool teachers in China aims to help protect adolescents from sexual violence.

The results of Paramastri et al., (2010) show that sexual violence in adolescents is not very familiar among teenagers and parents [5]. They think that sexual violence is the same as sexual harassment, namely a form of things that smell dirty, sexy, pornographic and pornographic. Although many mass media, both visual and audio, often display the problem of sexual violence against teenagers. However, the intensity of the news has not been able to meet the public's needs for matters relating to sexual violence against teenagers.

Sexual violence against adolescents is an urgent problem in global society that causes depression, unwanted pregnancies and HIV [6]. To respond to this global problem, policies have been adopted. The fundamental policy goal is to improve the prevention of sexual violence [7].

However, policymakers face difficult challenges as adolescent sexual violence tends to be hidden, complex, and sensitive [8]. Therefore, solutions to address adolescent sexual violence include raising awareness about adolescent sexual violence, and empathic responses to its victims. Providing adolescents with a correct understanding of sexual violence and providing materials on sexuality education can prevent adolescent sexual [9].

Providing sexuality education is an effort to reduce the number of victims of teenage sexual violence [10]. Materials such as not allowing other people to touch a teenager's private parts and telling teenagers that the right thing to do is to tell an adult if someone tries to sexually assault them and to run as far away as possible. Based on this phenomenon, sexuality education for adolescents needs to be carried out as early as possible, so that adolescents have a correct understanding of sexual violence and can protect themselves from sexual violence.

The sexuality education curriculum can stand alone or be integrated with other subjects. To support himself at school, activities outside of school are also important. To increase the success of sexuality education, it does not only depend on the school curriculum, but also the role of the family, community and government. Schools have limited time and supervision, so family guidance and community control play a greater role in forming a knowledgeable and moral generation.

Talking about sexuality education in the curriculum, we are not just talking about a particular approach, a particular teacher, or the doctrine of a particular expert, but all parties must be involved and given a special approach by combining issues of religion, nationality, morals, morals, humanity, and teaching about sexuality.

Sexuality education is not only limited to understanding sexual organs and their functions, but also as education about Islamic values and norms, permission to enter, lowering the gaze, guarding the private parts, separating teenagers' sleeping places, keeping teenagers away from promiscuity, teaching obligatory and sunnah bathing, explaining sexual issues. or adultery. If sexuality education is implemented through

schools, it will be clearer, more systematic and programmed. The application of integrated sexuality education in sociology learning in high school can provide knowledge and understanding through theories and concepts that are integrated with sexual education.

METHODS

The method used is a literature review which helps this research by providing an overview of current problems [11,12] and presenting the latest evidence in certain fields of science [13].

Literature reviews can be used to answer research questions by using guidelines in carrying out the steps in reviewing an article. Article sources were adopted from several reputable international journal databases and published Science and Technology Index (SINTA) journals.

The steps used start from a search using the keywords: sexual education, sexual education, and integration of sexual education with subjects. Next, after getting the article, carry out an analysis starting with; problems, objectives, methods, research findings, and recommendations.

Next, the data is processed through a systematic review process which includes the following steps: 1) database selection; 2) determining keywords; 3) screening manuscripts based on predetermined criteria, and (4) applying population criteria. Search efforts yielded a total of 79 articles. Based on the aim of analyzing sexual education studies through grouping; 1) FoSV; 2) Sexual education materials are integrated into the curriculum and subjects; 3) Integrating sexual education materials into sociology teaching materials is effective in preventing sexual violence; and 4) Recommend a model for integrating sexual education into sociological concepts for high school subjects. After going through a screening process, 45 articles were finally selected which were included in Tables 1 to Table 4, while 34 other articles were not included.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Review Literature

FoSV

Based on analysis of several review articles. Several forms of violence that occur in schools: Verbal Sexual Harassment, Inappropriate Physical Contact, Online Exploitation, Use of Power and Influence and Coercion or Rape. If you or someone you know has experienced sexual harassment at the hands of a teacher at a high school, it is important to immediately report it to the authorities and school authorities, such as the police, so that appropriate legal action can be taken against the perpetrator.

Apart from that, counseling support and psychological assistance are also very important for victims to help them overcome the trauma they may have experienced. Following are some findings sourced from articles that have been published in Table 1.

Table 1: (FoSV)

No	FoSV	Covers	Source
1.	Sexual Violence Against Children	Rape, Sexual Assault, Sexual Harassment, Intimidation, Teasing and Threats Against Children.	[14,15,16,17]
2.	Sexual Violence Against Women	Public Harassment, Flashing, Unwanted Groping, Forced Sex, Domestic Violence, Rape, Forced Marriage, Human Trafficking, Prostitution, Female Genital Mutilation, Intimidation, Attempted Rape, Forced Prostitution, Forced Pregnancy, Forced Abortion, Forced Marriage, Trafficking of Women For Sexual Purposes, Coercion of Women's Clothing and Discrimination Through Regulations.	[17,18,19,20,21,22,23,24,25]
3.	Sexual Violence Against Students	Rape, Sexual Abuse of Children, and Sexual Coercion Among College Students.	[16]
4.	Sexual Violence in an International Context	Marital Rape, Forced Reproduction, Inserting Objects into the Vagina or Anus, and Withholding Sexual Pleasure.	[27]
5.	Sexual Violence in the Context of Armed Conflict	Rape, Sexual Assault, Sexual Harassment, Stalking, Human Trafficking, Sexual Exploitation, Forced Abortion, Forced Marriage, Prostitution, Sexual Slavery, and Sexual Torture.	[26,27]

Table 1 explains the findings of several articles discussing sexual violence. Boetto (1992) explains that sexual violence includes physical sexual behavior that occurs without consent [28]. Furthermore, Amalia et al. (2021) stated that sexual violence includes actions such as harsh words, swearing, groping, kissing, hugging, and other unwanted actions, as well as physical violence such as beatings [29].

Ali (2017) describes various types of violence against children and women, including intimidation, teasing and threats [15]. Hotten (2019) found behaviors such as child sexual abuse, rape, and sexual assault [14]. In addition, Khusnaeny (2016) lists forced marriage, forced prostitution, forced pregnancy, and forced abortion as FoSV [21]. Additionally, Deosthali et al. (2022) discuss several forms of sexual violence against women, including but not limited to forced procreation, marital rape, insertion of items into the vagina or anus, and withholding of sexual pleasure [23]. In addition, Spowart (2020) reported FoSV including stalking and human trafficking [30]. Furthermore, Absori et al. (2020) added that FoSV include sexual exploitation, forced use of contraceptives, forced marriage, prostitution, sexual slavery and sexual torture [31]. According to Vijayalakshmi (2015), female genital mutilation and domestic abuse against women are common throughout Africa [19].

Violence frequently reported by women includes acts of harassment in public places, flashing behavior, groping and forced sexual intercourse [18]. Furthermore, distinct etiological pathways may be connected to child sexual abuse and sexual coercion among college students, as per Carvalho & Nobre's (2013) findings [16]. According to Franklin (2004), violence against homosexuals and gang-related rape of women can be viewed as parallel forms of cultural theater where the victims are interchangeable theatrical props [20].

Critics of sexual violence view securitization in international relations as an exceptional phenomenon and state that the fetishization of sexual violence in international advocacy and scholarship influences different power relations [27]. Examining the various impacts of sexual violence on victims whose psychological health will be disturbed, such as; mental disorders, depression, and leading to suicidal behavior [22,32]. The various FoSV that exist and their impact on victims of sexual violence require efforts to overcome them. Randall & Venkatesh (2015) emphasize the need to regulate laws against perpetrators of sexual violence as part of the human rights agenda to achieve gender equality [24].

Sexual violence is a serious problem that can occur in various contexts, such as in the household, academic environment, armed conflict situations, and community life in general. The impact of sexual violence is very complex and includes serious psychological impacts, such as mental disorders, depression and the risk of suicidal behavior. So prevention efforts provide law enforcement to perpetrators and provide education about the dangers and impacts in the school and community environment.

Sexual education material is integrated into the curriculum and subjects.

Regarding sexual education materials integrated into curricula and school subjects can be a useful approach, however special attention is needed in the preparation of materials and the involvement of experts to ensure their effectiveness in providing a comprehensive understanding of sexual issues in their context. Some of the articles analyzed can be seen in Table 2.

Table 2: Sexual Education Material is Integrated Into the Curriculum and Subjects

No	Sexual education material is integrated into the curriculum and subjects	Covers	Source
1.	Integration of Universal Values and General Treatment of Humans.	Emphasis on values relating to the general treatment of humans in teaching about sexual fantasies and "perversions." Preparation of children to be "good" sexual partners to prevent abuse	[33,34]
2.	Teaching through English.	Use of English as a means to teach topics such as healthy relationships, consent, sexual assault, and safe sex practices.	[35,36,37]
3.	Literary Initiative in Perspective Development.	Use of literary materials and initiatives to develop perspectives on sexuality and gender in lessons.	[38]
4.	Integration in Curriculum and Academic Disciplines.	Development of a broad understanding of sexuality from various points of view (anthropological, sociological, psychological, and ethical) in curricula and academic disciplines.	[34,37,39,40,41,42,43,44,45,46,47,48]
5.	Sexual Perspectives in Behavioral Science Courses.	Viewing sex in the context of students' overall life experiences in courses like Behavioral Science.	[49]
6.	Integration in Teacher Education.	Integrating gender and sexual diversity in teacher education to prepare teachers to face gender and sexual diversity in educational contexts.	[36,48]

Table 2 explains the integrated sexual education material. Integrating gender and sexual diversity into existing curricula and extracurricular activities can enhance learning and increase tolerance and understanding among students [41].

Teaching material about sexual fantasies and deviations is the most important aspect of sex education in preparing boys to be good sexual partners [33]. Integrating explicit sex education topics can improve students' sexual experiences and English literacy. For example, using poetry as a learning tool can explore topics such as healthy relationships and safer sexual practices [35].

Apart from that, this material is also structured to develop a learning model by adopting a critical and dialogic pedagogical approach. This approach can support teachers in implementing similar practices according to their respective contexts [38].

Sex education integrated into academic disciplines allows students to develop a broad understanding of sexuality from Anthropological, Sociological, Psychological, and Ethical viewpoints. Research conducted by Chisebe & Mphande (2023) shows that the integration of sex education in several subjects aims to increase students' awareness of sexual activity [50].

The findings of an in-depth review of the science of integrating gender and sexual diversity in teacher education are also shared, while preparing teachers to face today's unimaginable gender and sexual diversity [36].

In the context of courses such as Behavioral Sciences, students can explore their sexual experiences from a holistic life perspective. Some of these concerns may be expressed openly, while others may be discussed more generally [49]. This concern is a source of inspiration in integrating sexual education into the curriculum and subjects aimed at overcoming various forms of threats of sexual violence in schools and society. The strategies implemented in dealing with these challenges vary, which can provide valuable insights to improve implementation not only in these countries, but also in other low- and middle-income countries facing similar problems [39].

The importance of integrating sex education into the curriculum and extracurricular activities as a way to increase students' understanding of sexuality, promote tolerance, and reduce sexual violence, while also highlighting challenges and strategies to overcome obstacles to implementation.

Integrating sexual education into sociology teaching materials is effective in preventing sexual violence.

Several positive aspects related to the implementation of integrated sexual education learning in sociology teaching materials. Reflections on Integrated Sexual Education Learning in Sociology Teaching Materials. Increased Student Knowledge, Education on Prevention of Sexual Violence, Compliance with the Safe School Program, Student Comprehension in Writing and Potential for Reducing Cases of Sexual Harassment/Violence. Several related aspects are presented in Table 3.

Table 3: Integrating sexual education into sociology teaching materials is effective in preventing sexual violence

No	Integrating sexual education into sociology teaching materials is effective in preventing sexual violence	Covers	Source
1.	Overcoming the Roots of Problems and Patriarchal Structures.	Using comprehensive sexuality education in sociology teaching materials to teach about the root causes of sexual violence and how patriarchal structures influence these dynamics. This includes discussing concepts such as toxic masculinity and control over women's bodies.	[51,52,53,54]
2.	Encourages Critical Reflection and Communication Skills.	Incorporating elements of critical reflection in learning, allows students to question social norms that support sexual violence. Additionally, healthy communication skills can also be taught to help students identify and respond to potentially dangerous situations.	[55,56]
3.	Addressing Sexualization and Social/Emotional Learning.	Focus on teaching that addresses the sexualization of girls and women in general, as well as strengthening social and emotional learning to develop self-confidence and healthy boundaries in relationships.	[52,57,56, 58,59]
4.	Student and Survivor-Centered Teaching.	Adopting a student-centered approach allows space for students' experiences and perspectives to be acknowledged and integrated in learning about sexual violence. Including survivors' experiences can also provide valuable insight.	[51,52,60]
5.	Integrating Positive Sex Education Programs.	Incorporate sex-positive education programs such as "Relationships, Sexuality, and Violence Prevention" to increase understanding of healthy relationships and increase self-efficacy in self-defense.	[53,54,61,62,63, 64]

Table 3 explains that integrating sexual education into sociology teaching materials is effective. Comprehensive sexuality education can help prevent partner violence among youth by encouraging critical reflection, developing communication skills, and encouraging care-seeking behavior [55]. Implementing comprehensive sex education has also proven effective in preventing dating violence and encouraging social/emotional learning [57]. The implementation of several positive sexual education programs, Relationships, Sexuality, and Violence Prevention, also significantly increases female students' self-defense self-efficacy [63]. In addition, bystander programs also teach segments of the college community to get involved, become positive bystanders, raise awareness, and build skills to end sexual violence [54]. In addition, face-to-face programs have also been proven to produce positive behavioral changes in preventing sexual violence [64].

Taking into account several views that have been expressed, integrating moral education and sex education curricula can help prevent sexual violence by providing lessons to boys on how to express themselves sexually with morals [33]. Meanwhile, mandatory integration of prevention education into the teacher certification curriculum is also needed to increase teachers' understanding of sexual violence [64]. Integrating sexuality education into sociology teaching materials can help prevent sexual violence against adolescents by addressing the root of the problem and challenging patriarchal structures [51]. According to Moloney & Pelehach, (2014) Integrating sexual education into sociology teaching materials can also help prevent sexual violence by addressing the sexualization of girls and women [59]. In the teaching context, a student-centered approach and educator self-disclosure can provide space for educators, researchers, and students to engage together in preventing sexual violence [66]. Effective teaching must be dynamic and holistic, interrogating complex social realities, including experiences, to teach effectively about sexual violence [52]. Additionally, a student-centered approach to teaching about sexual violence can be more effective and avoid institutional betrayal than providing trigger warnings [60].

Integrating comprehensive sexuality education into the sociology curriculum can help prevent sexual violence against youth by addressing the root causes and challenging patriarchal structures. Using a student-centered approach, educator self-disclosure, and a survivor-centered approach are also needed in teaching about sexual violence in order to achieve optimal effectiveness.

Model for Integrating Sexual Education into Sociology Teaching Materials

This integration model was designed using several materials related to sexual violence that occurs in society, and several sociological concepts, namely: Conflict and Violence, Social Control, Deviant Behavior, Values and Norms, and Social Problems combined with sexual education material. The design model for integrating sexual education into sociology teaching materials can be seen in Fig 1 below.

Figure 1: Model for Integrating Sexual Education into Sociology Teaching Materials

From Figure 1 (a, b, c, d, e & f) above, for Figure 1 (a) the syntax of integrating sexual education with sociology subjects is based on; facts, concepts, principles and procedures. Meanwhile, Figure 1 (b - f) is an integration model of several concepts in sociology teaching materials that are integrated with sexual education. The model for integrating sexual education into sociology teaching materials has several important components. Teachers can include an understanding of sexual violence in conflict and social violence material, use case facts involving teachers as illustrations, explain sociological concepts related to violence, and present principles that explain the factors that trigger sexual violence. Apart from that, procedures for avoiding sexual violence by teachers must also be taught. Through sexual education which is integrated into sociology learning, it helps students understand and overcome this sensitive issue in a social context.

DISCUSSION

There are several forms of violence that occur in school settings, including verbal sexual harassment, inappropriate physical contact, online exploitation, use of power, and coercion or rape [67]. Such violence is not only physically and emotionally detrimental to the victim, but also violates the law as well as ethical norms that should be upheld in any society. Responses to sexual violence in schools are critical [68]. Actions taken should be in line with the illegality and unacceptability characteristic of this violence. Sexual violence is a serious violation of law and ethics that should not be trivialized.

The first step to take is to report cases of sexual violence involving teachers in schools to school authorities and authorities such as the police. It is important to enforce the law appropriately so that justice can be realized [69]. However, that is not all that is required. Victims also need emotional support, counseling, and psychological assistance to help them cope with the trauma that may arise from such traumatic experiences.

In addition to post-sexual violence measures, prevention is also very important [70]. Enhancements are required in the areas of sexual violence reporting, individual rights education, and the limits of appropriate interpersonal relationships. By doing so, society will be better able to prevent and mitigate similar cases of violence in the future. Furthermore, the development of clear and strong school policies to prevent and address sexual violence is essential [68]. In order to provide a secure atmosphere and shield kids from the possibility of sexual assault in schools, this policy should be backed by the necessary protocols.

The integration of sexual education in sociology materials has great potential to be a useful approach. However, special attention is needed in the preparation of materials and involving experts to ensure its effectiveness in providing a comprehensive understanding of sexual issues in the context of sociology [71]. The implementation of sexual education learning integrated in sociology materials can provide significant benefits in improving students' understanding of sexuality and preventing sexual violence [72]. However, it is necessary to continue to monitor and evaluate the effectiveness of this approach. Refinement of learning methods is also important in order to achieve the desired goals.

A crucial first step is to incorporate knowledge of sexual assault into resources about social conflict and violence [73]. This involves elucidating sociological themes linked to violence, offering principles that elucidate the circumstances that trigger sexual violence, and employing case studies with instructors as examples. Furthermore, it's critical to instruct educators on methods that help stop sexual assault. This integration helps students understand and address these sensitive issues in a broader social context. The integration of sexual education in sociology subjects provides an opportunity for students to gain a deeper insight into the complexity of sexual issues in society. However, it also demands extra attention to the curriculum developed, ensuring that the material taught is relevant, accurate and meets ethical standards in teaching sensitive issues. Finally, collaboration with experts in the field of sexual education and sociology is essential. They can provide greater insight and necessary guidance in developing appropriate materials and learning strategies to address sexual issues in the context of sociology.

CONCLUSIONS

A number of harmful behaviors against women and children are included under the major problem of sexual violence. Because sexual assault has psychologically complicated effects, it is crucial to incorporate sexual education into the curriculum and extracurricular activities to help kids understand sexuality, develop tolerance, and lessen sexual violence. Through a student-centered approach, educator self-disclosure, as well as programs such as; the relationship between sexuality and violence prevention, is also considered important to prevent sexual violence. Additionally, there is a need to integrate prevention education into the curriculum at every level of education. In this case the author recommends a model of integrating sexual education in sociological learning subjects, which links facts, concepts, principles and procedures aimed at integrative education which are considered relevant. It is hoped that this integration model can help students understand and overcome the problem of sexual violence in a social context through studying sociology in high school.

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